

The Diasporic Perspectiveness of Beast and Man's Fatal Agony in Yann Martel's Life of Pi

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The Canadian novel flourished as a powerful medium of expression for Diaspora or migrated people's world during the middle of the 20th century. The periodical power of regional forces inevitably played a prominent role to relocate people from one place to another in the world. Yann Martel gained full spread attention and acclaimed with the publication of his novel *Life of Pi*. The novel *Life of Pi* starts with the chapter author's note and the protagonist's Limbo-state of unexpected experience, as pi recounts events that occurred when he was 16 years old. The 'Pi' in the title is Piscine Molitor Patel, a middle-aged man who lives in Canada. Pi was the protagonist of *Life of Pi* was the precocious son of a pragmatic zookeeper, an Indian boy fascinated by his nation's many faiths but forced by its many political problems to immigrate to Canada along with his family and their animal charges from Pondicherry. During the voyage of migration, their ship suddenly wrecks, leaving the boy on a lifeboat along with few furry survivors; ultimately only Pi and a Tiger (Richard Parker) remain alive. As the duo drifts through the Pacific Ocean, struggling to survive the elements in voyage of the ocean, Pi most also struggle to escape his shipmate; he relies on his wits and his faith in, intermittently, Christianity, Hinduism, and Islam to do so. We never hear from the tiger again, but we do only hear from Pi. He retells his story as an adult living in Toronto, in a house whose decor- a portrait of our lady of Guadalye rests beside a photo of Kaaba; a brass statue of Shiva stands beneath; a prayer rug lies near a bedside bible. So the protagonist suffers from the dilemma of maniac migration of multi-religious belief.

Canada's dominant cultures were originally British and French, as well as aboriginal. After Prime Minister Trudeau's announcement of the implementation of the policy of multi-culturalism within a bilingual framework in 1971, Canada gradually became home to a more diverse population of readers and writers. The country's literature has been strongly influenced by international immigration, particularly in recent decades. Canada's research, whether written in English or French, often reflects the Canadian perspective on nature, frontier life, and Canada's position in the world. Canada's ethnic and

cultural diversity is reflected in its literature, with many of its most prominent writers focusing on ethnic life.

Margaret Atwood is probably the best known modern Canadian author. Other essential novelists during and after world war II include Morely Callaghan, Gwethalyn Graham, John Buell Hugh MacLennan, Mordecai Richler, Malcolm Lowry, Ethel Wilson, Robertson Davies, Brain Moore, Margaret Laurence, Timothy Findlay, Neil Bissoondath, and M.G.Vassanji. Many of their novels have focused attention on Canadian city life, social problems, and the significant problem of Canadian multi-cultural division.

Canada is divided into many regions – the Maritimes, Ontario, Alberta and Quebec, Saskatchewan, British Columbia, etc. Each region has its peculiarities which permeate the novels of writers living there.

Canada is the land of immigrants from England, France, India, China, Japan, Arab countries, Africa, etc. Hence, it is a land of multiracial and multi-cultural fusion, in which the immigrants assimilate their varied social and cultural values to form a national culture, but their consciousness has hidden sparks of their native culture and social benefits. Thus, Canadian literature has Diasporas' characters.

The mid-twentieth century novels deal with social reality. Mac Lennan's famous novel *Barometer Rising* is a realistic novel which graphically describes the destruction of Halifax, a great Canadian city during World War I. It presents a conflict between the pre-war and posts war Canada. Neil Marcrae, Penelope Wain and Angus Murray represent the war time Halifax, the symbol of the old colonial order. Colonel Wain, on the other hand, represents the new generation, the youth of Canada. Sinclair Ross's first novel *As for My House and Me* is memorable. Collin Mc Dougall's *Execution* is a realistic novel. And also the notable authors Alice Ann Munro and Yann Martel.

Martel then gained international recognition with *Life of Pi*, about the son in a family of Indian zookeepers and his journey to Canada. The resulting acclaim, including the Booker Prize, brought Martel an invitation to teach at the Free University of Berlin, Germany, which he accepted. In 2007, Martel began sending Canadian Prime Minister Stephan Harper a book every two weeks, reportedly out of concern that Harper was not in the habit of reading. By the time he stopped in 2011. Martel had sent Harper a total of 101 books, starting with Leo Tolstoy's *The Death of Ivan Ilyich* (1886) and ending with *In Search of Lost Time* (1996), a six-volume set by Marcel Proust.

Martel has been praised for his investigation of gender roles and the subjective nature of self and Diaspora cultural characters. Martel attained vast comprehension with the publication of his novel, *Life of Pi*. The 'Pi' in the title is Piscine Molitor Patel, a middle-aged man who lives in Canada. The story is mostly told in retrospect, as Pi recounts events that occurred when he was sixteen years old. As a boy, Pi's family decides to emigrate from India to Winnipeg. His father, the keeper of a municipal zoo in India, plans to bring some of the zoo's animals to Canada and sell them when he arrives. There is a shipwreck, and Pi is the only human survivor. He finds himself standing on a lifeboat with some of the animals, including a Zebra, a Hyena, an Orangutan and a Bengal tiger named Richard Parker. Over Pi's 227 days on the lifeboat, the food chain is demonstrated as the Hyena eats first the Zebra and then the Orangutan. The tiger then eats the hyena, and Pi feeds the rat to the tiger, train to keep him from being eaten. Pi realizes that the only way to key the tiger from eating him is to learn to coexist with Richard Parker. He marks his territory on the boat with urine and ultimately comes to love the tiger. Eventually, the ship comes ashore in Mexico, where Richard Parker runs off into the Mexican wilderness. Pi recounts his tale to local officials, who do not believe his story. He retells the story to them allegorically substituting people for the animals. Pi's tale of survival on the boat interspersed with discussions of philosophy and religion and doubt emerge as running themes in work.

The novel *Life of Pi* begins with the chapter Author's note. An anonymous author's figure explains that he traveled from his home in Canada to India because he was feeling restless. There, while sipping coffee in a café in the town of Pondicherry, he met an old man name Francis Adirubasamy who offered to tell him a story fantastic enough to provide him faith in god. This story is that of Pi Patel. The author then changes into the story itself, but not before expressing his reader that the account will come across more naturally if he says it in Pi's voice.

Part one is narrated in the first person by Pi. Pi describes from an advanced age, looking back at his earlier life as a high school and college student in Toronto, then even further back to his boyhood in Pondicherry. He tells that he has suffered intensely and found solace in religion and Zoology. He explains how Francis Adirubasamy, a close business associate of his father's and a competitive swimming champion, taught him to swim and bestowed upon in his unusual name. Pi is described after the Piscine Molitor, a Parisian swimming club with two pools that Adirubasamy used to frequent. We see that pi's father once ran the Pondicherry zoo, teaching Pi and his brother, Ravi, on the dangerous nature of animals by maintaining a live goat to a tiger before their young eyes. Pi, brought up as a Hindu, discovers Christianity, then Islam, choosing to practice all three religious simultaneously.

At the beginning of Part Two, the ship is beginning to sink. Pi clings to a lifeboat moreover encourages a tiger, Richard Parker, to join him. Then, recognizing his mistake in bringing a wild animal abroad, Pi leaps into the ocean. The narrative jumps back in time as Pi explains the explosive noise and chaos of the sinking: crew members throw him into a lifeboat, where he soon finds himself directly with a zebra, an orangutan and a hyena, all seemingly in shock. His family is gone. The storm subsides, and Pi sees his dark situation. The hyena kills the zebra and the orangutan, and then to pi's intense surprise- Richard Parker reveals himself: the tiger has remained in the bottom of the lifeboat all along. Soon the tiger kills the hyena and Pi, and Richard Parker is alone collectively at sea. Pi subsists on canned water, and filtered seawater, emergency rations and freshly caught sea life. He also gives for the tiger, whom he masters and trains.

The days pass slowly, and the life boat's passengers coexist warily. Through a bout of temporary blindness brought on by dehydration, Pi has a run-in with another blind castaway. The two discuss food and their boats to one another. When the blind man attacks Pi, intending to eat him, Richard Parker kills him. Not long after, the ship pulls up to a strange island of trees that grow directly out of vegetation, without any soil. Pi and Richard Parker stay here for a time, sleeping in their boat and exploring the island during the day. Pi discovers a massive colony of Meerkats who sleep in the trees and freshwater ponds. One day, Pi finds human teeth in a tree's fruit and concludes that the island eats people. He and Richard Parker head back to sea, finally washing ashore on a Mexican beach. Richard Parker runs off, and villagers take Pi to a hospital.

In part three two officials of the Japanese Ministry of Transport interview Pi of his time at sea, they are hoping to shed light on the fate of the doomed ship. Pi describes the story as above, but it does not fully satisfy the skeptical men. So he repeats it, this time following the animals with humans: a ravenous cook instead of a hyena, a sailor instead of a zebra and his mother instead of the orangutan. The officials note that the two stories match and the second is far likelier. In their definitive report, they commend Pi for living so long with an adult tiger.

Yann Martel's *Life of Pi* uses meticulously researched details about zoological oddities such as the eating and sleeping habits of sloths and tigers to lull readers into believing that the world Pi inhabits is rational. Pi's survival for 227 days in a lifeboat on the Pacific stretches credulity, but Martel is so detailed about the ordinariness of this ordeal that our disbelief is suspended. We even come to accept that it might just be possible that a 450 pound Royal Bengal tiger could be cowed into submission by the movement of the waves and the need to be fed. Martel tips his hand when

Pi lands on an island of self-sustaining, fresh-water generating algae covered in a veritable carpet of Meerkats. As delightful as this false paradise is, it is impossible, and not so pleasant either as Pi discovers to his horror. With this unsettling revelation about the unreality of Pi's world in mind, readers are then confronted in the final chapters with the overthrow of all that they have understood about the story. The ultimate challenge to readers is to which account they choose to believe. Is truth more than what we can see and measure? *Life of Pi* is an adventurous emigrational novel. It is a novel about religion, philosophy, science, and above all, the relationship between these things and Diasporas characters.

Many critics have regarded the book's resemblance to Yann Martel's novel *Life of Pi* with Ernest Hemingway's novel *The Old Man and the Sea*. Both stories have featured on an immigrant struggle between man and beast against fate. In *The Old Man and the Sea*, a sailor struggles to pull in a mighty marlin, while in *Life of Pi*, Pi and Richard Parker conflict for dominance on the lifeboat. Both the Pi and fisherman learn to respect their animal counterparts; each pair is connected in their mutual suffering, resolve, and strength. Although they are competitors, they are also partners, ally, even double, have the indifferent intention to elude from death.

Besides, both novels emphasize the importance of endurance of fatal migration in an irresistible natural force. Because death and destruction are inevitable, both books present life as a choice between only two options: defeat or endurance until destruction. Whatever the real story, Martel suggests Scliar in his Author's Note, thanking him for "the spark of life."

"Despair was a heavy blackness that let no light in or out. It was a hell beyond expression. I thank God it always passed. A school of fish appeared around the net, or a knot cried out to be reknotted. Or I thought of my family, of how they were spared this terrible agony. The blackness would stir and eventually go away, and God would remain, a shining point of light in my heart. I would go on loving". (209)

According to Pollock and Van, Reken TCK tends to struggle more than others with a "migratory instinct" because "an unrealistic attachment to the past, or a persistent expectation that the next place will finally be home, can lead to inner restlessness that keeps the TCK always moving" (125). Even though Martel's parents were Canadian, his father's position as a diplomat meant that Martel was born in Spain and "grew up in Alaska, British Columbia, Costa Rica, France, Ontario, and Mexico" (Sielke 12). As an adult Martel "spent time in Iran, Turkey, and India (12). In a sense, Martel writes the 'migratory instinct' into Pi's character by forcing Pi into a sense of rootlessness. Martel takes Pi from his home in India to the Pacific, then to Mexico, and finally has him settle in Canada, where he longs for the home that he had with his family. But this home does not exist longer.

Pi's experience illustrates that starvation is a physical sensation with emotional and metaphysical consequences. Initially, Pi is reduced to weeping over the first fish that he kills. Hunger and the desperation that results from starvation quickly alter Pi's attitude. He shifts from a timid vegetarian, respectful of all sentient life, to a vicious pescetarian, a vegetarian, who eats seafood. Two pages after he weeps over the death of his first kill he explains: "you may be astonished that in such a short period I could go from weeping over the muffled killing of a flying fish to gleefully bludgeoning to death a Dorado..." (185). Pi attributes this dramatic shift in his behavior to the simple and brutal truth that a person can get used to anything, even to kill. This moment in Pi's journey is one of the most apparent indicators that Pi's stories are about ethical truth.

Life of Pi is again instructive here. Recall at the outset that in addition to describing Pi as simultaneously a Hindu, Christian, and Muslim, it was also mentioned that he was a trained zoologist. This point of distinction is not incidental to the story and the development of its main character. For one, it provided a connection between Pi's old life in India and his new life in

Canada, giving some continuity to a life story tragically interrupted at sea. While growing up as a young boy, Pi's father owned and operated the city zoo. This intimate knowledge of the life of a zookeeper gave Pi the necessary know-how to survive the long ordeal adrift at sea sharing a lifeboat with his 450-pound tiger companion (or at least so Pi would have us believe). But it was also at least partly the cause of the ordeal in the first place. The reason Pi and his family were traveling by boat across the Pacific was that they were bringing their zoo animals with them to liquidate their family assets by selling off the animals to the highest North American bidders. At this time, God did not provide a haven for the renewal of his creation, but instead, Pi, his family and an entire boatload of animals worthy of a whole zoo were almost entirely lost at sea. And but for the ingenuity of the sixteen year- old Pi all would undoubtedly have been lost.

Pi, during his journey in the Pacific Ocean, had a devastating experience. He lost his family after the shipwreck. Though he survived, he was living with a wild animal which may devour him anytime. He almost lost hope because, in the vast Pacific, he believes that no one can rescue him. There were even times that he questioned God's existence, and he felt that he has abounded. With his experience, Pi almost gave up and almost stopped holding on to his faith.

The attempt by Pi's family to migrate to Canada is presented in a similar way to these zoo animal escapes, emphasizing the involuntary nature of some contemporary migrations. As he describes the family's preparations to leave India, Pi likens himself and his brother to zoo animals: "two animals were being shipped to the Canada Zoo. That's how Ravi and I felt. We did not want to go. We did not want to live in a country of gale-force winds and minus- two- hundred – degree winters (88). This comparison suggests some awareness of captive animal's lack of control (it might also refer to the removal of zoo animals from their natural climates). For Pi's father, the decision to leave has more in common with the discussion of the zoo animal's escapes. Pi says,

People go in the hope of a better life... Any business is a risky business and none more so than small business, the one that risks the shirt on its back... People move because of wear and tear and anxiety... Because of the feeling that nothing will change, that happiness and prosperity are only possible somewhere else. (77-79)

Pi explains that "In February 1976, the Tamil Nadu government was brought down by Delhi... it was to Father the crowning touch in Mrs.Indra Gandhi's dictatorial takeover of the nation."(78). Thus, the possible parallels with escaping zoo animals could be seen to liken the Patel's to animals in their incomplete autonomy. The boys are being moved against their will (initially) as zoo animals are, while their parents are moving only to get away from something, as animals are described as doing.

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